

Fact Sheet: Empowering the Workforce

TIMHWP Empowering the Workforce stream aims to empower the mental health workforce to deliver culturally safe and responsive care for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples. This is being achieved by building and strengthening the cultural responsiveness of mental health professionals and decolonising educational curricula, in addition to empowering the Aboriginal Social and Emotional Wellbeing (SEWB) workforce.

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National Project:

Australian Indigenous Psychology Education Project

The **AIPEP** is an innovative Aboriginal-led project pioneering the way in transforming and decolonising higher education psychology across Australia. The original AIPEP was undertaken from 2013 to 2016 and developed guidelines to:

- increase Indigenous content in psychology curricula,
- support Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples' participation in psychology,
- increase workforce capabilities in cultural responsiveness skills among the mental health workforce.

AIPEP has been revived under TIMHWP (Empowering the Workforce). AIPEP-2 aims to implement the findings from the original project to decolonise and transform psychology higher education and increase Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander student participation in psychology.

AIPEP-2 is:

- building and engaging with a national Community of Practice educators to empower higher education psychology professionals to transform their curricula. Currently, 32 higher education providers (HEPs) have joined, which is almost 80% of HEPs that offer APAC-accredited psychology courses!
- providing a suite of resources, workshops, and webinars to build staff and student capacity of cultural responsiveness with Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples
- conducting research to understand opportunities to improve curricula and support Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander psychology students.

The Stream 2 team include:

Professor Pat Dudgeon

Chief Investigator of
TIMHWP

Professor Jill Milroy

Head of School of
Indigenous Studies

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TIMHWP

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Jeneva Ohan**

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National Representation in AIPEP-2

AIPEP-2 has national representation from HEPs and industry partners across Australia. In addition, AIPEP-2 has national representation from peak psychology bodies, including: AIPA, APS, APAC, PsyBA, and HODSPA.

Indigenous governance and ethics have been at the forefront of project considerations, negotiations, and implementation. AIPEP-2 is led by respected Aboriginal psychologist and scholar Professor Pat Dudgeon and is informed by Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander organisations, including AIPA, IAHA, NACCHO and GDPISA, who form the Indigenous advisory committee for projects within AIPEP-2 and TIMHWP.

The Current Psychology Workforce

During the 2020/21 period, the number of psychologists were **41,817**, which represents an increase of **3.2%** from the previous financial year. Despite this, only **0.7%** (approximately **292**) of psychologists identified as Aboriginal and/or Torres Strait Islander.

The Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander population in Australia is **3.3%**. Therefore, to achieve parity, it is estimated a further **1087** Aboriginal and/or Torres Strait Islander psychologists are needed.

One of the AIPEP-2 targets is to increase the number of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander psychologists. Psychology students of today represent the emerging psychology workforce of the future. Aboriginal and Torres Strait students are more likely to choose psychology as a career path if Indigenous knowledges are included in curriculums.

To encourage participation and to build a culturally responsive psychological workforce, it is critical that the content is culturally relevant to meet the needs of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples and communities, including students and consumers.

Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander psychology students

Across the 2018 to 2020 period, we have seen a rise in Aboriginal and/or Torres Strait Islander student completions of undergraduate psychology (Level 1). On average, across Australia, Honours (Level 2) and Postgraduate (Levels 3-4) numbers indicate that a greater emphasis on the progression from undergraduate to Honours levels are needed to promote progression of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander students to entry into Postgraduate psychology.

Facilitating equitable participation of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander students in the study of psychology is multi-levelled and includes:

- building relationships with Indigenous Education Centers, Indigenous academics and scholars within and across providers, and partnerships with community organisations.
- Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander student pathways to Honours and Postgraduate psychology study and engaging in student lived experience,
- decolonising psychology curriculum and,
- engaging collaboratively with Elders and cultural advisors on a culturally responsive vision and plan for the HEP, that considers embedding cultural safety in the HEP, hiring Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander staff, and a roadmap to curriculum change.

Projects Underway

AIPEP 2 Research:

Two important research projects are underway. This research will contribute to an important body of knowledge regarding decolonising psychology educational curricula and facilitate the development of a curriculum change roadmap.

Systematic Review: This review aims to identify and analyse relevant literature regarding decolonising approaches in psychology education.

Scoping Study: Representatives from HEPs offering a psychology program will be invited to share their experiences of:

- increasing cultural responsiveness with Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples in the psychology curricula and
- approaches taken to support Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander student participation in psychology.

Psychology Supervisor Guide:

We are collaborating with AIPA to develop a psychology supervisor guide, intended for Ahpra board approved psychology supervisors (estimated 1000 across Australia). The guide will aim to promote and support psychology supervisees' cultural responsiveness in working with Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples, and in the provision of culturally responsive supervision with Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander psychology supervisees.

Wiley Indigenous Psychology Book Chapter:

With the aim to build understanding of Indigenous psychology in Australia, and student cultural responsiveness, the Wiley book chapter project (2021-2022) involved (1) writing an Indigenous Psychology book chapter for inclusion in the renewed 6th edition Wiley Burton et al. Psychology textbook, (2) creating an interactive learning module to support the book chapter, and (3) will involve creating a set of teacher resources to support the cultural responsive teaching of the Indigenous Psychology book chapter. This chapter has now been completed, with a release date for the book expected in August 2022. Stay tuned on our social media platforms for more information!

Pearson Australia Video & Textbook Project:

The Pearson textbook project (2021-2023) aims to promote Indigenous psychology and build the capacity and cultural responsiveness of psychology students. The project involves (1) three Indigenous psychology videos, (2) a new Indigenous Psychology chapter for the renewed 4th edition first year Pearson Psychology textbook, and (3) provide Indigenous executive review to all chapters to ensure Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander knowledges and content has been incorporated throughout chapters of the 4th edition.

Projects Underway (cont.)

Australian Psychology Accreditation Council (APAC) Working Party on Cultural Responsiveness:

In 2019, APAC released a new standard requiring all HEPs with an accredited psychology program to demonstrate how they are embedding cultural responsiveness into their curriculum. The AIPEP 2 team have been actively participating in a working party tasked to provide guidance and exemplars of how HEPs can meet and exceed the accreditation Standard.

Other Projects

1. AHCWA partnership and SEWB project:

We have partnered with the Aboriginal Health Council of Western Australia (AHCWA) to co-design and co-develop research that aims to map SEWB workforce needs and build SEWB service capacity and delivery in the Aboriginal Community Controlled Health Service (ACCHS) sector. Together, this research aims to improve Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples' and communities' mental health and SEWB and build long-term, sustainable service capacity.

2. UWA SPS partnership:

We have been working closely with the UWA School of Psychological Science (SPS) to embed Indigenous knowledges throughout the psychology course curricula and support Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander psychology students. Through our partnership, we have provided consultation on learning material and course content, held presentations with SPS staff, and begun yarning circles between TIMHWB and SPS to promote a two-way learning and sharing process, to build cultural awareness and responsiveness.

3. SEWB Gathering:

Our first SEWB Gathering, held in March 2021, brought together delegates from across Australia to discuss SEWB for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples. TIMHWB, Gayaa Dhuwi (Proud Spirit) Australia, NACCHO, and AIPA hosted the SEWB Gathering, with the aim to have a national discussion about SEWB with Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander organisations and groups. A number of actions arose from the first Gathering, including the development of an SEWB Network and Clearing House and renewal of the SEWB Framework which will be subsumed by the Close the Gap Coalition of Peaks Partnership SEWB Target.

The second SEWB Gathering was held again in October 2021. Day 2 of the SEWB Gathering focused on the SEWB ACCHS workforce and the mainstream mental health workforce, led by Lance Reilly (Nunkuwarrin Yunti) and Tom Brideson (Gayaa Dhuwi Proud Spirit Australia). Planning for the third SEWB Gathering is now underway.

To stay updated with the findings of the Gatherings, see: <https://timhwb.org.au/sewb-gathering-reports/>

References:

- (1) Australian Health Practitioner Regulation Agency. (2021). Annual Report 2020/21. Australian Health Practitioner Regulation Agency.
- (2) Australian Bureau of Statistics. (2018). Estimates of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Australians. [tinyurl.com/umsem5tf](https://www.abs.gov.au/tourism)
- (3) Information provided by the Australian Government Department of Education, Skills, and Employment (2022).

Learn more about AIPEP-2 and search the library of resources on our website:

indigenouslypsych.org.au

AIPEP
Australian Indigenous
Psychology Education Project
www.indigenouslypsych.org.au

Our partners:

